

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16

**MoS₂ quantum dots for on-line fluorescence determination of the food additive
allura red in beverage**

Alicia Coloma^a, María del Pozo^{a*}, Rut Martínez-Moro^a, Elias Blanco^a, Pedro Atienzar^b,
Lorenzo Sánchez^c, María Dolores Petit-Domínguez^a, Elena Casero^a, Carmen Quintana^a

^a*Departamento de Química Analítica y Análisis Instrumental, Universidad Autónoma de
Madrid, Cantoblanco, 28049 Madrid, Spain.*

^b*Instituto Universitario de Tecnología Química CSIC-UPV, Departamento de Química,
Universidad Politécnica de Valencia, 46022 Valencia, Spain.*

^c*Departamento de Medio Ambiente. Geología Ambiental Aplicada. CIEMAT. Avda.
Complutense, 40 Edif. 85, 28040 Madrid. Spain*

*maria.delpozo@uam.es; Phone: +34 914975916; Fax: +34914974931

17 **Abstract**

18 This work presents an on-line fluorescence method for the allura red (AR)
19 determination. The method is based on the fluorescence quenching of dots of MoS₂
20 because of their interaction with the non-fluorescence dye. MoS₂-dots were synthesized
21 and characterized by spectroscopic techniques and High Resolution Transmission
22 Electronic Microscopy (HR-TEM). The simultaneous injection of the nanomaterial and
23 the dye in a flow injection analysis system allows the determination of allura red at 1.7
24 $\times 10^{-6}$ M concentration level with a very good accuracy and precision (Er minor than
25 10% and RSD lower than 8%) and a sampling frequency of 180 samples per hour.
26 Moreover, the interaction fluorophore-quencher results a dynamic inhibition
27 mechanism. The proposed methodology was applied to the AR analysis in soft
28 beverages and powders for gelatine preparation. Colourant concentrations of 63 ± 2 mg/L
29 ($n=3$) and 0.30 ± 0.01 mg/g ($n=3$) were found, respectively. These results were validated
30 by high performance liquid chromatography technique.

31 **Keywords:** Molybdenum disulfide, dots, fluorescence inhibition, allura red, food
32 additive, flow injection analysis.

33

34

35

36 **1. Introduction**

37 Transition metal dichalcogenide (TMDs) nanomaterials are currently attracting the
38 interest of the scientific community because of their promising utilities. TMDs present
39 chemical formula of MX_2 , where X belongs to a chalcogenide group, M is a transition
40 metal and both make layers where the metal is located between two layers of
41 chalcogenides, as a sandwich. The adjacent MX_2 layers are bonded through Van der
42 Waals forces, so this weak interaction allows these nanomaterials to be easily exfoliated
43 to thin layers. Therefore, several TMDs nano-morphologies have been reported that can
44 be categorized in different dimensionalities as sheets (2D), nanoribbons and nanotubes
45 (1D) or dots and nanoparticles (0D) (Li et al., 2016). Although many combinations of M
46 and X have been disclosed, molybdenum disulfide and tungsten disulfide are the most
47 frequently employed TMDs. (Bouša et al., 2018; Coleman et al., 2011; S. Xu, Li, &
48 Wu, 2015; X. Zhang et al., 2015)

49 TMDs nanostructures are produced following bottom-up or top-down approaches.(Sun
50 et al., 2017) Bottom-up syntheses are based on the reaction of metal transition salts with
51 chalcogenide ions, while the stacked structure of bulk TMDs makes them feasible to
52 top-down methods. The most common top-down approach is the ultrasonic-assisted
53 liquid exfoliation in appropriated solvents as N-methyl-pyrrolidone (NMP),
54 dimethylformamide (DMF) or ethanol/water. The advantages of this strategy are such as
55 cheap, easy, scalable and effective, efficiency that is boosted for solvents that minimize
56 the exfoliation enthalpy as NMP. (Huang, Zeng, & Zhang, 2013; Lesnyak, Gaponik, &
57 Eychmu, 2013)

58 Nanosheets and dots made of TMDs have exhibited their usefulness in the analytical
59 discipline. (Sinha et al., 2018; Vilian et al., 2019) The intrinsic TMDs-dots
60 photoluminescence has encouraged fluorescence methodologies while 2D-TMDs are

61 more likely to be employed for the development of electrochemical sensors (Vilian et
62 al., 2019). The former approach is based on the ability of some analytes to absorb the
63 photons that dots emit so the output is the dots signal quenching. (Cao et al., 2018; Guo,
64 Wang, Wu, Ni, & Kokot, 2015; X. Liu et al., 2018; Yong Wang & Ni, 2014; Zhao et al.,
65 2017) From this point of view, colourants could be good candidates as analytes in
66 quenching-based methodologies due to their inherent absorption properties.

67 Colourants are additives in a wide variety of foodstuff giving colour and improving
68 their organoleptic properties. These additives can be classified as natural, semisynthetic
69 and synthetic. Chlorophylls, carotenoids or anthocyanins (natural colourants) are
70 harmless but scarcely resistant to temperature changes, pH or solar radiation
71 (Damodaran, Parkin, & Fennema, 2007). For this reason, synthetic colourants are
72 widely used. This kind of additives are easily synthesized, stable and cheap (Bişgin,
73 2019). In addition, the sulphonic groups that are present in their chemical structure
74 confer them high solubility in water. The main disadvantage of synthetic colourants is
75 that they usually present azo groups together with aromatic rings in their structures, so
76 they are potentially carcinogens and allergens and can cause hyperactivity in children
77 (Carocho, Barreiro, Morales, & Ferreira, 2014; Ivani de Andrade et al., 2014). Some of
78 these azo-colourants are tartrazine (E-102), sunset yellow (E-110), ponceau 4R (E-124)
79 and allura red (E-129). Its analytical determination has been accomplished by several
80 techniques but especially by high performance liquid chromatography with UV-Vis
81 detector (HPLC-UV-Vis), UV-Vis spectrometry and electrochemical techniques
82 (Bişgin, 2019; Ivani de Andrade et al., 2014; Magerusan et al., 2018). Although
83 colourants are not usually fluorescent, indirect methods based on the interaction with
84 nanomaterials have demonstrated their success (H. Xu, Yang, Li, Zhao, & Liao, 2015).

85 Flow injection analysis (FIA) is appealing when fast, simple and efficient method is
86 required in routinely performed analysis. These procedures allow automation and
87 miniaturization of analytical methodologies so they have been recognized as very useful
88 in areas such as environmental, industrial and/or clinical analysis. The simple use of its
89 instrumentation makes FIA methods attractive to researchers in the development of
90 analytical methodologies with on-line detection. In addition, a great variety of detectors
91 have been successfully coupled with FIA systems (Trojanowicz & Kołacińska, 2016).

92 In this work, MoS₂-dots were synthesized and evaluated against the colourant Allura
93 red, employed as food additive. As a result, an on-line FIA method for the
94 determination of this non-fluorescent synthetic dye is developed. The method is based
95 on the fluorescence inhibition of MoS₂-dots due to the interaction with the analyte. The
96 Allura red concentration is monitored thanks to the simultaneous injection of the
97 nanomaterial and the colourant in the flow system. The development of a flow method
98 based on this interaction for the fast and sensitive analysis of non-fluorescent analytes
99 with high sample frequency, results a promising strategy that can be extended to
100 different non-optically active compounds of interest.

101 **2. Materials and Methods**

102 2.1 Reagents

103 Molybdenum disulfide powder (90 nm, 99%), quinoline yellow, sunset yellow,
104 ponceau 4R, carmoisine, amaranth, sodium citrate, sodium chloride, quinine, glucose,
105 fructose and allura red were obtained from Sigma Aldrich (www.sigmaaldrich.com). N-
106 methylpyrrolidone (NMP), orthophosphoric acid, methanol for HPLC, ammonium
107 acetate, acetone and sodium hydroxide were purchased from Scharlab, Spain
108 (www.scharlab.com). Nitric acid for measurements by ICP-MS was tri-distilled

109 commercial concentrate from Scharlab. Water was purified with a Millipore Milli-Q-
110 System. All solutions were prepared just before use. Inorganic Ventures
111 (Christiansburg, USA) supplied the certified reference molybdenum (995 ± 6 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)
112 standard for ICP-MS analysis.

113 2.2 Apparatus

114 For the MoS_2 -dots synthesis, an ultrasound bath (Transonic 570/H Elma) was used.
115 Both, a spectrophotometer Shimadzu UV-1800 and a spectrofluorometer Hitachi F-
116 7000 were employed for optical measurements. A pH meter Methrom C831 (Herisau
117 Switzerland) was used for buffers preparations. The Flow Injection Analysis system
118 employed consisted of i) a peristaltic pump (Heidolph 5201), ii) a 12 ports injection
119 valve (Teknokroma Analítica S.A) equipped with two loops that allows the
120 synchronized injection of nanomaterial and the analyte, converging both at the
121 beginning of iii) the reactor tube producing a homogeneous solution of both reagents
122 and iv) the spectrofluorometric detector operating at fixed excitation and emission
123 wavelengths. A High Performance High Resolution (Element 2) (Thermo Scientific)
124 was employed for Inductively Coupled Plasma - Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS)
125 measurements. Before the ICP-MS measurements, an acid purification system from
126 Savillex (Eden Prairie, USA) was employed for nitric acid tri-distillation.

127 High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) measurements were performed
128 with a Jasco Analytica PU-1580 high pressure pumping system, equipped with an
129 injector Rheodyne Model 7125, a 20 μL loop and a Kromasil C18 column (150 x 4.6
130 mm; 5 μm ; Scharlau). A Perkin Elmer 785A UV/VIS was employed as detector of the
131 chromatographic system.

132 High Resolution Transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM) images were acquired
133 with a transmission electron microscope (JEOL JEM 2100F, Tokyo, Japan) under an
134 accelerating voltage of 200 kV. Samples were prepared by applying one drop of the as-
135 synthesised nanodots in NMP onto a carbon-coated copper TEM grid, and allowing it to
136 dry at room temperature. TEM images were analyzed by using Gatan Digital
137 Micrographs software.

138 2.3 Procedures

139 *2.3.1. MoS₂-dots synthesis*

140 MoS₂-dots were synthesized following a previously reported method (S. Xu, Li, & Wu,
141 2015) with slight modifications: around 100.00 ± 0.01 mg of the bulk MoS₂ reagent was
142 added to 10.0 mL of NMP and the suspension was exfoliated in an ultrasound bath
143 during 3 h and then heated at 140 °C under stirring during 6 h. After leaving to rest
144 overnight, the mixture was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 45 minutes. MoS₂-dots were
145 separated in the supernatant and kept at 4 °C until use. From the ICP-MS analysis of the
146 as-prepared nanomaterials, it was found a synthesis yield of 2.02%.

147 *2.3.2. Spectroscopic measurements*

148 Absorbance spectra were acquired between 250 and 800 nm with a 1 cm quartz cuvette.
149 For spectrofluorometric measurements, an excitation wavelength (λ_{ex}) of 370 nm was
150 employed with a slit of 5.0 nm and the fluorescence was recorded from 380 to 600 nm
151 with 1 cm path length when static measurements were performed.

152 The MoS₂-dots concentration was quantified by ICP-MS. To this end, after the solvent
153 evaporation, the MoS₂-dots were dissolved in a 1:1 (v/v) HNO₃:HCl mixture, as
154 previously described in the literature (W. Zhang et al., 2015). After an adequate
155 dilution, the samples were subjected to ICP-MS determination. The Mo quantification

156 was performed at low resolution (LR) at $m / \Delta M = 300$. The tune parameters employed
157 were: plasma power = 1258 Watt, pump speed=15 rpm, cool gas = 16 L/min, auxiliary
158 gas =1.3 L/min, sample gas = 1.2 L/min, extraction voltage = -2000 V, SEM = 1900 V.
159 Mass spectrometric data were acquired in EScan mode at the following conditions:
160 segment duration = 0.15 s, settling time = 0.001 s, sample time = 0.015 s, samples per
161 peak = 50, acquired points = 10, detection mode = analogical + counting, integration
162 window = 20%. The isotope ^{95}Mo was monitored, in a mass range of 94.874 - 94.937 u
163 and with the same mass window of 20%. Sample introduction was performed with a
164 peltier cooled inlet system with quartz cyclonic spray chamber (ESI: Elemental
165 Scientific Instruments, Omaha EEUU).

166 FIA measurements were carried out with fluorescence detection at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 370$ nm and an
167 emission wavelength (λ_{em}) of 475 nm. $\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4/\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4$ 0.1M buffer pH =2 was
168 employed as carrier solution pumped at a constant flow rate of 3 mL/min. A volume of
169 100 μL of MoS_2 -dots (150 fold diluted in water) and 100 μL of analyte were
170 synchronously injected in the flow system and the successive reaction was produced in
171 a 40 cm reactor with an internal diameter of 0.5 mm.

172 HPLC-UV measurements were performed following a previously reported procedure
173 (Yu & Fan, 2016) with a flow rate of 0.7 mL/min.

174 2.3.3. *Sample preparation*

175 Two commercially samples were acquired in a local market, a carbonated drink and a
176 powder for gelatine preparation. The soft drink of strawberry flavour was degassed
177 under stirring and, after 10 times dilution with carrier solution, was injected in the FIA
178 system. For HPLC-UV analysis, the carbonate drink samples were degassed as
179 described above and diluted (1:10) with Methanol/ammonium acetate 0.02 M (35/65,

180 v/v) employed as mobile phase. Next, the diluted samples were filtered through a 0.45
181 μm pore size nylon filter before injection in the chromatographic system.

182 An accurate amount of gelatine sample of around 3.00000 ± 0.00001 g was crushed
183 with a mortar. The sample was successively extracted first with methanol and then with
184 acetone by tip sonication according to a published procedure (Shen, Zhang,
185 Prinyawiwatkul, & Xu, 2014). After centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 5 minutes, the
186 extracts were mixed up and evaporated under nitrogen stream until nearly dryness. The
187 residue was reconstituted in methanol and filled up to 5.00 mL. Before to be injected in
188 the FIA system, 150 μL of the extract were diluted to 1.00 mL in the carrier solution.
189 For HPLC analysis, 15 μL of the sample extract were diluted with mobile phase to 5.00
190 mL before filtration and injection.

191

192 **3. Results and discussion**

193 3.1 Nanomaterials characterization

194 *3.1.1. High-Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy experiments*

195 The synthesized dots of MoS_2 were characterized by HR-TEM to obtain information
196 related to its particle size and crystallinity. Figure 1A shows an example of the HR-
197 TEM images obtained where individual and very small nanoparticles of around 5 nm or
198 minor, are observed. Moreover, in the marked zone of the image, the lattice fringes
199 revealing the nanoparticles crystallinity can be clearly observed, also Fast Fourier
200 Transform (FFT) analysis support this observation. From the data of $N = 90$
201 nanoparticles, a mean diameter of (3.4 ± 0.9) nm was calculated. The electron
202 diffraction (SAED) pattern of the inset in Figure 1A reveals the hexagonal lattice

203 structure with a lattice parameter of 0.27 nm (calculated from inverse FFT image after
204 selecting the diffraction spots) and similar with the direct measurement of profile plot
205 (Figure 1B and 1C), consistent with the (100) diffraction planes of MoS₂ (Ha, Han,
206 Choi, Park, & Seo, 2014; Q. Liu, Hu, & Wang, 2016; Yichao Wang et al., 2013).

207 FIGURE 1 HERE.

208

209 3.1.2. Spectroscopic characterization

210 First, the MoS₂-dots concentration was evaluated by the ICP-MS procedure described
211 above. Figure S1 depicts the calibration graphs corresponding to the Mo determination.
212 From this analysis, the concentration MoS₂-dots was 0.202 mg/mL.

213 Next, the MoS₂-dots synthesized in NMP were subjected to spectroscopic
214 characterization after a 1:100 dilution in water. The MoS₂-dots UV-Vis spectrum
215 (Figure S2A) displays two absorption bands centred at 270 and 340 nm. These two
216 bands are the maxima characteristic of TMDs-dots and are ascribed to the electronic
217 transitions of π to π^* and n to π^* , respectively (X. Liu et al., 2018). Notice that no
218 features were recorded at longer wavelengths. Unlike TMDs-dots, TMDs-nanosheets
219 show up to four absorption bands in the 390-680 nm domains so the effective
220 transformation of nanolayers into dots can be concluded (X. Liu et al., 2018; Wilcoxon,
221 Newcomer, & Samara, 1997; H. Xu et al., 2015; S. Xu et al., 2015a). Moreover, as
222 stated in the introduction section, TMDs-dots have inherent photoluminescence (Štengl
223 & Henych, 2013). For this reason, it was recorded the emission spectra at different
224 excitation wavelengths around both UV-Vis maximums. The spectra in Figure S2B
225 confirm that: i) a luminescent nanomaterial was synthesized as expected; ii) irrespective
226 of the excitation wavelength (λ_{exc}) used, MoS₂-dots present an emission band with a

227 maximum at 458 nm (λ_{em}); iii) the fluorescence intensity depends on λ_{exc} , recording the
228 highest intensities when exciting at λ_{exc} 270 and 370 nm.

229 The influence of the pH of the solution on the MoS₂-dots fluorescence was tested by
230 varying the pH solution in which the dots suspension was diluted. Figure S3 depicts the
231 results corresponding to MoS₂-dots excitation at 370 nm. As observed, the fluorescence
232 intensity decreases as pH increases, recording the maximum fluorescence value at acidic
233 media. Moreover, the fluorescence signal is not affected by the presence of salts in
234 solution as can be concluded by comparing the spectra recorded in un-buffered water
235 and neutral pH phosphate buffer. It should be noted the large decrease in the signal
236 showed at alkaline conditions. This pH dependence was also observed when 270 nm
237 λ_{exc} was used (data not shown). As the highest intensity signal is obtained with 0.1 M
238 H₃PO₄/NaH₂PO₄ pH 2, this pH was selected as the measurement medium for the rest of
239 experiments.

240 In this pH 2 medium, we calculated the relative fluorescence quantum yield of the
241 MoS₂-dots, employing quinine as standard (Φ tabulated λ_{exc} 275 nm = 0.577) and
242 according to equation 1 below:

$$\Phi_x = \Phi_s \frac{A_s}{A_x} \cdot \frac{F_x}{F_s} \cdot \left(\frac{n_x}{n_s}\right)^2$$

243 **Equation 1.** Φ = fluorescence quantum yield, A = absorbance at λ_{exc} , F = emission
244 curve area, n = solvent refraction index. Subscripts *s* and *x* correspond to the standard
245 and the analyte respectively.

246 From the results, a value of 8.6% was obtained which is similar or better than other
247 values previously reported in the literature for MoS₂-dots and carbon dots (Cao et al.,
248 2018; Yong Wang & Ni, 2014; Z. Wang & Dai, 2015).

249

250 3.2 MoS₂-dots interaction with Allura red. Static conditions.

251 The absorbance spectrum of a 2.0×10^{-5} M AR solution shows two absorption bands
252 between 300 and 600 nm (Figure 2A, curve a). However, it is important to note that no
253 fluorescence is registered for this dye neither when exciting at its maximum absorption
254 wavelength (500 nm) or exciting at the MoS₂-dots excitation wavelength (270 and 370
255 nm) (data not shown). In addition, Figure 2A includes the fluorescence spectra of MoS₂-
256 dots (dotted lines). As can be seen, these emission spectra overlap in a great extent with
257 the absorption spectrum of the colourant. This result led us to expect an interaction
258 between the nanomaterial and the AR based on the energy/photon transfer of MoS₂-dots
259 emission to the colourant.

260 FIGURE 2 HERE

261 To verify the interaction of the nanomaterial with AR, the fluorescence spectra of a
262 solution containing a mixture of both, MoS₂-dots and AR, were registered either at $\lambda_{exc} =$
263 270 nm or $\lambda_{exc} = 370$ nm. Figure 2B shows the fluorescence response of the dots and the
264 dots in presence of 2.0×10^{-5} M of AR at $\lambda_{exc} = 370$ nm. As observed, the nanomaterial
265 fluorescence is greatly quenched in presence of AR probably because of the analyte
266 absorbs the nanomaterial emission leading to a fluorescence reduction in a dynamic
267 mechanism as will be latter discussed. The same behaviour is observed when excitation
268 is performed at 270 nm (data not shown). We selected 370 nm as excitation wavelength
269 since better selectivity is expected than working at lower excitation conditions.

270 Once the nanomaterial-AR interaction was experimentally confirmed, a deeper study of
271 this interaction was carried out. The Stern-Volmer constant (K_{sv}) determines the degree

272 of interaction fluorophore - quencher (Lakowicz, 2006) and it is calculated from the
273 same name equation:

$$\frac{If_0}{If} = 1 + K_{sv}[Q]$$

274 **Equation 2.** Stern-Volmer equation.

275 In this equation, If_0 and If correspond to the MoS₂-dots emission in absence and in
276 presence of a concentration of colourant, $[Q]$. The meaning of the calculated constant is
277 that the higher the K_{sv} value, the stronger the interaction. For K_{sv} determination, the
278 MoS₂-dots spectrum was registered in presence of increasing concentrations of AR.
279 Figure 3 shows the obtained results of If_0/If versus AR concentration. The monitoring of
280 the dots emission was performed at λ_{em} of 475 nm where the quenching due to the
281 interaction with AR is more remarkably produced (see Figure 2B). This experiment was
282 performed at different temperature values.

283 FIGURE 3 HERE

284

285 As shown in Figure 3, linear relations between If_0/If and AR concentration are obtained
286 in all experiments. From the corresponding slopes, the K_{sv} values can be calculated (see
287 the legend Figure 3). Data shows a slight increase in K_{sv} with the temperature. This
288 increase would imply a dynamic inhibition mechanism in which diffusion could control
289 the interaction. This diffusion is favoured by increasing the temperature, making greater
290 the constant value (X. Liu et al., 2018).

291 Finally, the influence of the concentration of MoS₂-dots was studied to obtain the best
292 analytical response in terms of sensitivity. To this aim, several nanomaterial dilutions
293 (1:50-1:200) in 0.1 M H₃PO₄/NaH₂PO₄ pH 2 were prepared and assayed against two
294 analyte concentration levels, $[AR] = 1.25 \times 10^{-6}$ M and $[AR] = 2.00 \times 10^{-5}$ M (data not

295 shown). From the results, the best accomplishment was obtained for a 150-fold dilution.
296 Therefore, this condition was selected for the development of the FIA analytical method
297 towards the on-line AR determination.

298 3.3 MoS₂-dots interaction with AR in flow conditions. FIA experiments.

299 FIA measurements were carried out with fluorescence detection at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 370$ nm and an
300 emission wavelength (λ_{em}) of 475 nm. Figure S4 shows that the synchronized injection
301 of MoS₂-dots and AR produces a decrease in the height peak confirming the interaction
302 MoS₂-dots-AR in the carrier flow towards the fluorescence detection system. This
303 simple experiment allows us to conclude that the quenching effect can be monitored
304 also under flow conditions. Therefore, the optimization of the experimental variables
305 affecting to the FIA system was following made.

306

307 *3.3.1. FIA optimization: hydrodynamic and geometric parameters.*

308 The hydrodynamic and geometric parameters involved in the FIA response were
309 optimized in order to obtain the highest fluorescence quenching ($\% \text{If}_0 = \frac{\text{If}}{\text{If}_0} \cdot 100$) as
310 well as the highest sample frequency. Caudal (Q), reactor length (L), reactor internal
311 diameter (Di) and injection volume (V_{inj}) were optimized. First, the influence of the
312 carrier flow rate was evaluated in the 1 to 4 mL/min range. The results did not show a
313 noticeable influence in the $\% \text{If}_0$ but the sample frequency increases while increasing the
314 caudal, because of the decrease of the peak width (Figure S5). This effect is produced
315 up to a flow rate value of 3 mL/min, when the signal is stabilized. Therefore, this flow
316 rate was considered as optimal for the rest of experiments.

317 Six reactors were used to optimize length (L = 40, 70 and 100 cm) and internal diameter
318 (Di = 0.5 and 0.8 mm). As seen in Figure S6, the thinnest internal diameter reactor
319 showed better %If₀ regardless of the length. For each Di value, a shortened reactor
320 showed a slightly better %If₀. In base of these results, a reactor with Di = 0.5 mm and L
321 = 40 cm was selected for the analytical determination.

322 Sample loops were simultaneously varied between 50 and 200 μL volume keeping the
323 same volume for the analyte and the MoS₂-dots. As in previous experiments, %If₀ was
324 scarcely affected. However, it was found that the higher the loop volume, the wider the
325 FIA signal peaks so poorer sampling frequencies were registered. From the results
326 (Figure S7), 100 μL volume was fixed for further assays. Altogether, the optimal
327 parameters summarized in Table S1 allow the analysis of 180 samples/h in conjunction
328 with a good fluorescence inhibition.

329 *3.3.2. Influence of AR concentration in the analytical response. Analytical data*

330 Once all the variables affecting the FIA system were optimized, the quenching in the
331 fluorescence intensity of MoS₂-dots with increasing AR concentrations was studied.
332 Figure 4 shows that a linear decrease of the initial signal was obtained in the AR
333 concentrations range of 5.00×10^{-6} M to 4.00×10^{-5} M according to the equation: %If₀ =
334 $-1.2 (\pm 0.3) \times 10^6 [\text{AR}] (\text{M}) + 99.0 (\pm 0.6)$; r=0.995.

335 FIGURE 4 HERE

336 Detection limit (LOD) and determination limit (LOQ) for the analytical method were
337 calculated from the standard deviation (σ) of 10 injections of MoS₂-dots in the FIA
338 system and the slope of the corresponding linear range of the calibration curve. The
339 obtained values were 1.7×10^{-6} M and 5.6×10^{-6} M for LOD (3σ/slope) and LOQ
340 (10σ/slope), respectively. These results are comparable with those reported in the

341 literature for the AR determination with different analytical methodologies (see Table
 342 S2) (Al Shamari et al., 2020; Deroco, Medeiros, Rocha-filho, & Fatibello-filho, 2018;
 343 Mazdeh et al., 2016; Rodriguez, Ibarra, Miranda, Barrado, & Santos, 2016; Silva,
 344 Garcia, Lima, & Barrado, 2007; Tang et al., 2018; Vidal, Garcia-Arrona, Bordagaray,
 345 Ostra, & Albizu, 2018). Compared with the analytical methods summarized in Table S2,
 346 the proposed method presents several advantages such as allowing a fast analysis with a
 347 high sample frequency and the possibility of an on-line analysis automation.

348 Table 1 summarizes the results obtained to evaluate the accuracy and the precision in
 349 terms of the relative error (Er %) and the relative standard deviation (RSD %). The
 350 precision was assessed in both, repeatability and reproducibility for five concentrations
 351 levels. As seen, the developed method presents Er (%) values lower than 10% and
 352 excellent results in terms of repeatability and reproducibility with RSD (%) values
 353 lower than 1.3% and 8%, respectively.

354

355 **Table 1.** Er (%) and RSD (%) for the developed method at different AR concentrations.

[AR] (M)	Er (%)	RSD (%) _(n=3) repeatability	RSD (%) _(n=3) reproducibility
1.25×10^{-5}	4.0	0.6	3
1.50×10^{-5}	6.7	0.7	4
2.00×10^{-5}	10	0.3	6
3.00×10^{-5}	3.3	1.2	8
4.00×10^{-5}	5.5	1.3	7

356

357 3.3.3. Interference study

358 The selectivity of the method was evaluated by the change that it is produced in the
 359 fluorescence signal of a mixture of MoS₂-dots with 2.00×10^{-5} M of AR in presence of
 360 increasing amounts of different compounds that can be present in a sample together

361 with the analyte. It was considered that interference is produced at a concentration level
362 that led to a change in the initial analytical signal bigger than the relative error of the
363 method (10%). Sodium citrate, sodium chloride, glucose and fructose were selected
364 because they are usually found in carbonated drinks. Both salts can be present in high
365 concentration respect to AR, even to 200-fold, without produce interference.
366 Concerning glucose and fructose, the obtained results show that the maximum
367 concentrations allowed without producing interference are 0.37 M and 0.055 M,
368 respectively. These results show the possibility to determine AR in presence of high
369 concentration of sugar. The rest of compounds assayed were other colourants that can
370 also appear with the analyte in some samples. Amaranth, quinoline yellow, ponceau 4R,
371 carmoisine and sunset yellow interfere for a concentration higher than 2.80×10^{-5} M,
372 2.03×10^{-5} M, 8.03×10^{-6} M, 1.50×10^{-5} M and 2.00×10^{-5} M, respectively. These
373 results show that it is possible to determine AR in presence of other colourants.

374

375 *3.3.4. Application to AR determination in real samples.*

376 The feasibility of the method was tested towards the AR determination in real samples
377 of a commercial carbonated drink of strawberry flavour and a powder to prepare
378 gelatine. The procedures for each sample preparation were previously detailed in the
379 experimental section. In the case of the carbonated drink, only a degas pre-treatment of
380 the beverage was needed. The determination was carried out by the injection in the FIA
381 system of non-spiked samples and samples spiked with increasing AR concentrations.
382 The FIagrams in Figure 5 show the decrease produced in the MoS₂-dots fluorescence
383 intensity when the non-spiked sample was injected. This fact allows us to conclude the
384 presence of AR in the selected sample, as it was described in the available information
385 of the drink. As expected, the fluorescence quenching linearly increases with increasing

386 amounts of AR added according to the equation: $\%If_0 = (-1.2 \pm 0.6) \times 10^6 [AR] (M) +$
387 (82.5 ± 0.7) ; $r = 0.994$. As observed, the slope obtained with the standard addition
388 method is the same than that gotten with the external calibration procedure described
389 before. This fact suggests that no matrix interference was produced. Therefore, the
390 external calibration was employed to determine the AR concentration in the sample
391 obtaining a value of 63 ± 2 mg/L ($n = 3$) of AR in the beverage. Due to the legal limit
392 established by the Council of the European Union of AR in this kind of samples is 100
393 mg/L, this sample is appropriate for human consumption (Union, 1994). The recovery
394 of the method was evaluated from the analysis of an initially spiked sample at 2.00×10^{-5}
395 M AR concentration. A recovery of 105% with a RSD of 3.8% as average of three
396 independent analyses was calculated.

397 For the AR determination in gelatine samples, aliquots of 150 μ L of non-spiked and
398 spiked with increasing AR amounts sample extracts (obtained as described in section
399 2.3.3.) were diluted to 1.00 mL and injected in the FIA system. In this case, a linear
400 decrease of the % If with the increase of AR fitted with the equation: $\%If = 85.4 \pm 0.3 -$
401 $(6.03 \pm 0.09) \times 10^5 [AR] (M)$. The difference in the slope observed with respect to that
402 obtained with the calibration graph $(-1.2 (\pm 0.3) \times 10^6 M^{-1})$, shows the influence of these
403 matrix in the AR determination. Therefore, the colourant concentration was calculated
404 from the addition standard procedure. An AR amount of 0.30 ± 0.01 mg/g ($n=3$) was
405 obtained in this sample with a recovery of 96%, evaluated at 2.00×10^{-5} M
406 concentration level.

407 FIGURE 5 HERE

408

409

410

411

412 3.3.5. HPLC-UV-Vis experiments

413 In order to validate the result obtained by the FIA-based methodology, both the
414 carbonated drink and the powder for preparation of gelatines were further analysed by
415 HPLC-UV-Vis detection following a procedure previously reported (Yu & Fan, 2016).
416 Figure S8 shows the chromatographs corresponding to increasing AR concentrations.
417 As observed, AR was detected at a retention time (t_R) of 7.6 min and the increase of the
418 signal with AR concentration. Under these conditions, the area values recorded for the
419 injection of the samples, prepared as described before, were $(2.18 \pm 0.01) \times 10^5$ for the
420 carbonated drink and $(1.65 \pm 0.03) \times 10^4$ in the case of the gelatine sample. From the
421 slope of the calibration curve $(1.76 \pm 0.8) \times 10^{10}$ Area/ M), AR concentrations of $61.4 \pm$
422 0.3 mg/L (n=3) and 0.297 ± 0.006 mg/g (n=3) were respectively obtained. These results
423 are in very good agreement with that found with the FIA method proposed allowing us
424 to confirm that the herein reported method works for routine determination of this food
425 additive in real samples.

426

427 4. Conclusions

428 In this work, we have demonstrated that dots of MoS₂ results an interesting
429 nanomaterial for the analytical method development based on its fluorescence
430 properties. The HR-TEM reveals very small nanoparticles of 3.4 nm with a hexagonal
431 lattice structure consistent with the (100) diffraction planes. This nanomaterial presents
432 a fluorescence response with a maximum centred at 458 nm when excited with an
433 excitation wavelength of 370 nm. The inhibition of the MoS₂-dots fluorescence signal is

434 produced due to the interaction with the dye AR as analyte. The simultaneous injection
435 of the nanomaterial and the analyte in the flow system allows monitoring of the AR
436 concentration. After parameters optimization, the obtained results reveal a sensitive
437 method with a LOD of 1.7×10^{-6} M and a sample frequency of 180 samples/h. This
438 method was applied in the AR determination in a carbonated commercial drink and
439 powder for gelatine with a recovery of 105 % and 96%, respectively. These results were
440 in good agreement with the obtained with a HPLC-UV-Vis method.

441 **5. Acknowledgements**

442 The authors acknowledge financial support from the Spanish MICINN (MAT2017-
443 85089-C2-2-R), the Comunidad Autónoma de Madrid (P2018/NMT-4349,
444 TRANSNANOAVANSENS-CM).

445

446 **6. References**

- 447 Al Shamari, Y. M. G., Alwarthan, A. A., Wabaidur, S. M., Khan, M. A., Alqadami, A.
448 A., & Siddiqui, M. R. (2020). New Ultra Performance liquid chromatography-mass
449 spectrometric method for the determination of allura red in soft drinks using
450 corncob as solid phase extraction sorbent: Analysis and food waste management
451 approach. *Journal of King Saud University - Science*, *32*(1), 1135–1141.
452 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksus.2019.10.011>
- 453 Bişgin, A. T. (2019). Simultaneous Extraction and Determination of Allura Red (E129)
454 and Brilliant Blue FCF (E133) in Foodstuffs by Column Solid-Phase
455 Spectrophotometry. *Journal of AOAC International*, *102*, 181–188.
- 456 Bouša, D., Mayorga-Martinez, C. C., Mazánek, V., Sofer, Z., Boušová, K., & Pumera,
457 M. (2018). MoS₂ Nanoparticles as Electrocatalytic Labels in Magneto-

458 Immunoassays. *ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces*, 10(19), 16861–16866.
459 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b01607>

460 Cao, H., Huang, Y., Xie, Y., Shi, W., Fu, C., & He, W. (2018). A fast-responsive
461 fluorescent probe for sensitive detection of graphene oxide based on MoS₂
462 quantum dots. *The Analyst*, 143(13), 3107–3113.
463 <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8AN00849C>

464 Carocho, M., Barreiro, M. F., Morales, P., & Ferreira, I. C. F. R. (2014). Adding
465 Molecules to Food , Pros and Cons : A Review on Synthetic and Natural Food
466 Additives. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 13, 377–399.
467 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12065>

468 Coleman, J. N., Lotya, M., O’Neill, A., Bergin, S. D., King, P. J., Khan, U., Young, K.,
469 Gaucher, A., De, S., Smith, R. J., Shvets, I. V., Arora, S. K., Stanton, G., Kim, H-
470 Y., Lee, K., Kim, G. T., Duesberg, G. S., Hallam, T., Boland, J. J., Wang, J. J.,
471 Donegan, J. F., Grunlan, J. C., Moriarty, G., Shmeliov, A., Nicholls, R. J., Perkins,
472 J. M., Grievson, E. M., Theuwissen, K., McComb, D. W., Nellist, P. D., Nicolosi,
473 V. (2011). Two-Dimensional Nanosheets Produced by Liquid Exfoliation of
474 Layered Materials. *Science*, 331(6017), 568–571.
475 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1194975>

476 Damodaran, S., Parkin, K. L., & Fennema, O. R. (2007). *Food Science and Technology*.
477 Florida:Boca Ratón, (Chapter 1).

478 Deroco, P. B., Medeiros, R. A., Rocha-filho, R. C., & Fatibello-filho, O. (2018).
479 Selective and simultaneous determination of indigo carmine and allura red in
480 candy samples at the nano-concentration range by fl ow injection analysis with
481 multiple pulse amperometric detection. *Food Chemistry*, 247(November 2017),
482 66–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2017.12.006>

483 Guo, X., Wang, Y., Wu, F., Ni, Y., & Kokot, S. (2015). The use of tungsten disulfide
484 dots as highly selective, fluorescent probes for analysis of nitrofurazone. *Talanta*,
485 *144*, 1036–1043. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2015.07.055>

486 Ha, H. D., Han, D. J., Choi, J. S., Park, M., & Seo, T. S. (2014). Dual Role of Blue
487 Luminescent MoS₂ Quantum Dots in Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer
488 Phenomenon. *Small*, *10*(19), 3858–3862. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.201400988>

489 Huang, X., Zeng, Z., & Zhang, H. (2013). Metal dichalcogenide nanosheets:
490 preparation, properties and applications. *Chemical Society Reviews*, *42*(5), 1934–
491 1946. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c2cs35387c>

492 Ivani de Andrade, F., Florindo Guedes, M. I., Pinto Vieira, Í. G., PereiraMendes, N. F.,
493 Salmito Rodrigues, P. A., Costa Maia, C. S., Marqués Ávila, M. M., de Matos
494 Ribeiro, L. (2014). Determination of synthetic food dyes in commercial soft drinks
495 by TLC and ion-pair HPLC. *Food Chemistry*, *157*, 193–198.
496 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2014.01.100>

497 Lakowicz, J. R. (2006). *Principles of Fluorescence Spectroscopy*. New York, (Chapter
498 8)

499 Lesnyak, V., Gaponik, N., & Eychmu, A. (2013). Colloidal semiconductor nanocrystals:
500 the aqueous approach. *Chemical Society Reviews*, *42*, 2905–2929.
501 <https://doi.org/10.1039/c2cs35285k>

502 Li, B. L., Wang, J., Zou, H. L., Garaj, S., Lim, C. T., Xie, J., Li, N. B., Leong, D. T.
503 (2016). Low-Dimensional Transition Metal Dichalcogenide Nanostructures Based
504 Sensors. *Advanced Functional Materials*, *26*(39), 7034–7056.
505 <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201602136>

506 Liu, Q., Hu, C., & Wang, X. (2016). A facile one-step method to produce MoS₂
507 quantum dots as promising bio-imaging materials. *RSC Advances*, *6*(30), 25605–

508 25610. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6ra00572a>

509 Liu, X., Zhang, W., Huang, L., Hu, N., Liu, W., Liu, Y., Li, S., Yang, C., Suo, Y.,
510 Wang, J. (2018). Fluorometric determination of dopamine by using molybdenum
511 disulfide quantum dots. *Microchimica Acta*, 185(4).
512 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-018-2771-0>

513 Magerusan, L., Pogacean, F., Coros, M., Socaci, C., Pruneanu, S., Leostean, C., & Pana,
514 I. O. (2018). Green methodology for the preparation of chitosan / graphene
515 nanomaterial through electrochemical exfoliation and its applicability in Sunset
516 Yellow detection. *Electrochimica Acta*, 283, 578–589.
517 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2018.06.203>

518 Mazdeh, F. Z., Moradi, Z., Moghaddam, G., Moradi-Khatoonabadi, Z., Aftabdari, F. E.,
519 Badaei, P., & Hajimahmoodi, M. (2016). Determination of synthetic food colors,
520 caffeine, sodium benzoate and potassium sorbate in sports drinks. *Tropical Journal*
521 *of Pharmaceutical Research*, 15(1), 183–188. <https://doi.org/10.4314/tjpr.v15i1.25>

522 Rodriguez, J. A., Ibarra, I. S., Miranda, J. M., Barrado, E., & Santos, E. M. (2016).
523 Magnetic solid phase extraction based on fullerene and activated carbon adsorbents
524 for determination of azo dyes in water samples by capillary electrophoresis.
525 *Analytical Methods*, 8(48), 8466–8473. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6ay02631a>

526 Shen, Y., Zhang, X., Prinyawiwatkul, W., & Xu, Z. (2014). Simultaneous determination
527 of red and yellow artificial food colourants and carotenoid pigments in food
528 products. *Food Chemistry*, 157, 553–558.
529 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2014.02.039>

530 Silva, M. L. S., Garcia, M. B. Q., Lima, J. L. F. C., & Barrado, E. (2007). Voltammetric
531 determination of food colorants using a polyallylamine modified tubular electrode
532 in a multicommutated flow system. *Talanta*, 72(1), 282–288.

533 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2006.10.032>

534 Sinha, A., Dhanjai, Tan, B., Huang, Y., Zhao, H., Dang, X., Chen, J., Jain, R. (2018).
535 MoS₂ nanostructures for electrochemical sensing of multidisciplinary targets: A
536 review. *TrAC - Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 102, 75–90.
537 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2018.01.008>

538 Štengl, V., & Henych, J. (2013). Strongly luminescent monolayered MoS₂ prepared by
539 effective ultrasound exfoliation. *Nanoscale*, 5, 3387–3394.
540 <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3nr00192j>

541 Sun, J., Li, X., Guo, W., Zhao, M., Fan, X., Dong, Y., Xu, C., Deng, J., Fu, Y. (2017).
542 Synthesis Methods of Two-Dimensional MoS₂: A Brief Review. *Crystals*, 7(7),
543 198. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst7070198>

544 Tang, Y., Sun, Z., Shen, J., Yu, J., Wang, S., Hao, J., Wang, B., Huang, Y., Liu, X.,
545 Zhuang, H. (2018). Peptide modified gold nanoclusters as a novel fluorescence
546 detector based on quenching system of detecting Allura red. *Analytical Methods*,
547 10, 5672–5678. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c8ay01494a>

548 Trojanowicz, M., & Kołacińska, K. (2016). Recent advances in flow injection analysis.
549 *The Analyst*, 141(7), 2085–2139. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5AN02522B>

550 Union, C. of the E. (1994). European Parliament and Council Directive 94/35/EC of 30
551 June 1994 of sweeteners for use in foodstuffs. [https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-](https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/576c6110-0270-429a-b445-8bdb40025cb4/language-en)
552 [detail/-/publication/576c6110-0270-429a-b445-8bdb40025cb4/language-en.](https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/576c6110-0270-429a-b445-8bdb40025cb4/language-en)

553 Vidal, M., Garcia-Arrona, R., Bordagaray, A., Ostra, M., & Albizu, G. (2018).
554 Simultaneous determination of color additives tartrazine and allura red in food
555 products by digital image analysis. *Talanta*, 184(December 2017), 58–64.
556 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2018.02.111>

557 Vilian, A. T. E., Dinesh, B., Kang, S. M., Krishnan, U. M., Huh, Y. S., & Han, Y. K.

558 (2019). Recent advances in molybdenum disulfide-based electrode materials for
559 electroanalytical applications. *Microchimica Acta*, 186, 203.
560 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-019-3287-y>

561 Wang, Yichao, Ou, J. Z., Balendhran, S., Chrimes, A. F., Mortazavi, M., Yao, D. D.,
562 Field, M. R., Latham, K., Bansal, V., Friend, J.R., Zhuiykov, S., Medhekar, N. V.,
563 Strano, M. S., Kalantar-Zadeh, K. (2013). Electrochemical control of
564 photoluminescence in two-dimensional MoS₂ nanoflakes. *ACS Nano*, 7(11),
565 10083–10093. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nn4041987>

566 Wang, Yong, & Ni, Y. (2014). Molybdenum disulfide quantum dots as a
567 photoluminescence sensing platform for 2,4,6-trinitrophenol detection. *Analytical*
568 *Chemistry*, 86(15), 7463–7470. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac5012014>

569 Wang, Z., & Dai, Z. (2015). Carbon nanomaterial-based electrochemical biosensors: An
570 overview. *Nanoscale*, 7(15), 6420–6431. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5nr00585j>

571 Wilcoxon, J. P., Newcomer, P. P., & Samara, G. A. (1997). Synthesis and optical
572 properties of MoS₂ and isomorphous nanoclusters in the quantum confinement
573 regime. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 81(12), 7934–7944.
574 <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.365367>

575 Xu, H., Yang, X., Li, G., Zhao, C., & Liao, X. (2015). Green Synthesis of Fluorescent
576 Carbon Dots for Selective Detection of Tartrazine in Food Samples. *Journal of*
577 *Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 63(30), 6707–6714.
578 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.5b02319>

579 Xu, S., Li, D., & Wu, P. (2015a). One-pot, facile, and versatile synthesis of monolayer
580 MoS₂ /WS₂ quantum dots as bioimaging probes and efficient electrocatalysts for
581 hydrogen evolution reaction. *Advanced Functional Materials*, 25(7), 1127–1136.
582 <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201403863>

583 Yu, Y., & Fan, Z. (2016). Magnetic solid-phase extraction coupled with HPLC for the
584 determination of Allura Red in food and beverage samples. *Food Additives and*
585 *Contaminants - Part A*, 33(10), 1527–1534.
586 <https://doi.org/10.1080/19440049.2016.1231937>

587 Zhang, W., Wang, Y., Zhang, D., Yu, S., Zhu, W., Wang, J., ... Wang, J. (2015). A
588 one-step approach to the large-scale synthesis of functionalized MoS₂ nanosheets
589 by ionic liquid assisted grinding. *Nanoscale*, 7(22), 10210–10217.
590 <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5nr02253c>

591 Zhang, X., Lai, Z., Liu, Z., Tan, C., Huang, Y., & Li, B. (2015). A Facile and Universal
592 Top-Down Method for Preparation of Monodisperse Transition-Metal
593 Dichalcogenide Nanodots. *Angewandte Chemie*, 54, 5425–5428.
594 <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201501071>

595 Zhao, M., Chen, A.-Y., Huang, D., Chai, Y.-Q., Zhuo, Y., & Yuan, R. (2017). MoS₂
596 Quantum Dots as New Electrochemiluminescence Emitters for Ultrasensitive
597 Bioanalysis of Lipopolysaccharide. *Analytical Chemistry*, 89(16), 8335–8342.
598 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.7b01558>

599
600

601 **Figure Captions**

602

603 **Figure 1.** (A) HR-TEM image of the MoS₂-dots with 10 nm scale. The inset shows a
604 selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern. (B) Higher magnification showing the
605 lattice fringes of a MoS₂-dots. (C) A line profile indicating the d-spacing in the selected
606 MoS₂-dots.

607 **Figure 2.** (A) Absorption spectra of AR (a) and fluorescence spectra of MoS₂-dots at
608 different λ_{exc} (dotted lines). (B) Fluorescence spectra of MoS₂-dots in absence (a) and in
609 presence of 2.0×10^{-5} M AR (b). $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 370$ nm. MoS₂-dots diluted 1:100 in
610 H₃PO₄/NaH₂PO₄ 0.1M pH 2.

611 **Figure 3.** Fluorescence inhibition at 475 nm for increasing AR concentrations at
612 different temperatures. The legend includes the K_{sv} values calculated from the slopes
613 of the corresponding experiments.

614 **Figure 4.** A) FIagrams of MoS₂-dots and MoS₂-dots with increasing concentrations of
615 AR. B) Calibration plot of %I_{f0} with increasing concentration of AR. L= 40 cm; Di =
616 0.5 mm; Q = 3 mL/min; V_{inj} = 100 μ L. MoS₂-dots 1:150 in H₃PO₄/NaH₂PO₄ 0.1M pH 2.
617 $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 370$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 475$ nm.

618 **Figure 5.** FIagrams of MoS₂-dots and MoS₂-dots with non-spiked and spiked samples
619 L= 40 cm; Di = 0.5 mm; Q = 3 mL/min; V_{inj} = 100 μ L. MoS₂-dots 1:150 in
620 H₃PO₄/NaH₂PO₄ 0.1M pH 2. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 370$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 475$ nm.

621

622

623

624

Supplementary Material

MoS₂ quantum dots for on-line fluorescence determination of the food additive allura red in beverage.

Alicia Coloma^a, María del Pozo^{a*}, Rut Martínez-Moro^a, Elias Blanco^a, Pedro Atienzar^b, Lorenzo Sánchez^c, María Dolores Petit-Domínguez^a, Elena Casero^a, Carmen Quintana^a

^a*Departamento de Química Analítica y Análisis Instrumental, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Cantoblanco, 28049 Madrid, Spain.*

^b*Instituto Universitario de Tecnología Química CSIC-UPV, Departamento de Química, Universidad Politécnica de Valencia, 46022 Valencia, Spain.*

^c*Departamento de Medio Ambiente. Geología Ambiental Aplicada. CIEMAT. Avda. Complutense, 40 Edif. 85, 28040 Madrid. Spain*

*maria.delpozo@uam.es; Phone: +34 914975619; Fax: +34914974931

Figure S1. ICP-MS calibration graphs corresponding to Mo determination in the synthesized suspensions

Figure S2. A: UV-VIS absorption spectrum of MoS₂-dots 1:100 diluted in water. B: MoS₂-dots fluorescence spectra recorded at λ_{exc} between 260-380 nm.

Figure S3. MoS₂-dots spectra recorded for 1:100 dilution at different pH values. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 370$ nm.

Figure S4. FIA-graphs of MoS₂-dots and MoS₂-dots-AR. [AR] = 2.0×10^{-5} M; H₃PO₄/NaH₂PO₄ 0.1 M pH2; MoS₂-dots diluted 1:150 in H₃PO₄/NaH₂PO₄ 0.1 M pH 2. Reactor length (L) = 40 cm; Reactor internal diameter (Di) = 0.5 cm; Injection volume (V_{inj}) = 100 μ L; Caudal (Q) = 1 mL/min; $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 370$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 475$ nm.

Figure S5. % If₀ and sampling frequency variation with the carrier flow rate. L = 40 cm; Di = 0.5 cm; V_{iny} = 100 μL. MoS₂-dots 1:150 in H₃PO₄/NaH₂PO₄ 0.1M pH 2. [AR] = 2.00·10⁻⁵ M, λ_{exc} = 370 nm; λ_{em} = 475 nm.

Figure S6. Influence of both, length and internal diameter of the reactor, in the % If₀. V_{iny} = 100 μL; Q = 3 mL/min. MoS₂-dots 1:150 in 0.1M H₃PO₄/NaH₂PO₄ pH 2. [AR] = 2.00·10⁻⁵ M, λ_{exc} = 370 nm; λ_{em} = 475 nm.

Figure S7. Variation of both, % I_{f_0} and sampling frequency, with the injection volume. $L = 40$ cm; $D_i = 0.5$ mm; $Q = 3$ mL/min. MoS_2 -dots 1:150 in $\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4/\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4$ 0.1M pH 2. $[\text{AR}] = 2.00 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M, $\lambda_{exc} = 370$ nm; $\lambda_{em} = 475$ nm.

Figure S8. Chromatograms corresponding to solutions containing increasing concentrations of AR recorded at the HPLC-UV-Vis system (a) Mobile phase, (b) $2.0 \cdot 10^{-7}$, (c) $1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$, (d) $2.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$, (e) $4.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$, (f) $6.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$, (g) $8.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$, (h) $1.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$, (i) $1.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M, (j) $1.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M and (k) $2.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M.

Table S1. Hydrodynamic and geometrical parameter optimization.

Parameter	Range assays	Optimal value
[MoS ₂ -Dots] (dilution 1:X)	50-200	150
Flow rate (Q) (mL/min)	1-4	3
Reactor length (L) (cm)	40-100	40
Reactor internal diameter (Di) (mm)	0.5-0.8	0.5
Injection volume (V _{inj}) (μL)	50-200	100

Table S2. Comparative methods for AR determination

Method	LOD (mol/L)	Linear Range (mol/L)	Reference
Digital image analysis	1.29×10^{-6}	$4.29 \times 10^{-6} - 5.57 \times 10^{-5}$	(Vidal, Garcia-Arrona, Bordagaray, Ostra, & Albizu, 2018)
Amperometric-FIA (polyallylamine - GCTE)	1.40×10^{-6}	$1.00 \times 10^{-5} - 1.50 \times 10^{-4}$	(Silva, Garcia, Lima, & Barrado, 2007)
MPA-FIA (BDD/p-silicon)	7.00×10^{-9}	$4.00 \times 10^{-8} - 7.70 \times 10^{-7}$	(Deroco, Medeiros, Rocha-filho, & Fatibello-filho, 2018)
MSPE-CE	4.29×10^{-6}	$1.29 \times 10^{-5} - 8.58 \times 10^{-5}$	(Rodriguez, Ibarra, Miranda, Barrado, & Santos, 2016)
AuNCs-Peptide Fluorescence	6.67×10^{-7}	$2.00 \times 10^{-6} - 9.00 \times 10^{-5}$	(Tang et al., 2018)
UPLC-MS	2.57×10^{-8}	$1.00 \times 10^{-7} - 2.79 \times 10^{-6}$	(Al Shamari et al., 2020)
HPLC-UV	1.09×10^{-6}	-	(Mazdeh et al., 2016)
MoS ₂ -dots FIA-fluorescence	1.70×10^{-6}	$5.00 \times 10^{-6} - 4.00 \times 10^{-5}$	This work

GCTE: Glassy carbon tubular electrode; MPA-FIA: Multiple pulse amperometric Flow injection analysis. BDD/p-silicon: Boron-doped diamond/ p-silicon; MSPE-CE: Magnetic solid phase extraction coupled to capillary electrophoresis; AuNCs-Peptide: gold nanoclusters modified with peptide; UPLC-MS: Ultra performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry; HPLC-UV: High performance liquid chromatography couple to ultraviolet detector